

Professor Dr Mahmoud Moghavvemi

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6447-4203>

- **Also known as**

محمود مقومي , Professor Mahmoud

- **Websites & Social Links**

[Google Scholar](#)

[SCOPUS](#)

[Researchgate](#)

[LinkedIn](#)

[Academia](#)

- **Country**

Malaysia

- **Keywords**

Electronic circuit design, Applied Electronics, Sensors, Automation and control, Power and Energy systems, Voltage Stability, Power System Analysis

- **Other IDs**

[Scopus Author ID: 7003701545](#)

- **Email**

mahmoud@um.edu.my

Biography

Professor Dr. Mahmoud Moghavvemi graduated from the State University of New York (SUNY) at Buffalo with a B.Sc.(CIE) and B.Sc.(Electrical Engineering). He obtained his M.S degree from Bridgeport University and later on a Ph.D from the University Malaya where he is currently serving as full professor in the Department of Electrical Engineering ranked 23 in QS world University ranking. Prof. Mahmoud Moghavvemi was a committee member in establishing the University of Malaya's Bachelor of Engineering in (Telecommunications and biomedical) degree program. He also established the Computer Engineering degree program and was the director of the program for three years. Besides teaching duties prof Moghavvemi is actively involved in various research projects. He has registered more than forty patents and has published more than 250 articles in numerous technical journals and conferences. He is the founder and Director of University of Malaya center for research in applied electronics (CRAE)

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- **University of Malaya Faculty of Engineering: Kuala Lumpur, Wilayah Persekutuan, MY**

| Professor/ Director (Electrical Engineering)

Employment

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Source:Professor Dr Mahmoud Moghavvemi

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- **University at Buffalo - The State University of New York: Buffalo, NY, US**

Education

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